

nu se petrece însă la întâmplare, ci în mod argumentat și analitic de fiecare dată. Aparatul critic este deosebit de bogat și îngrijit, revelând acribia și seriozitatea cu care temele au fost abordate. Bibliografia lucrării, indexul temelor, cel al surselor și cel al autorilor moderni încheie la fel de riguros și științific cartea de față.

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Charles ALLEN, *The Buddha and Dr Führer: An Archaeological Scandal*, New Delhi, etc.: Penguin Books India, 2010, xii+292 pp. [first published in UK by Haus Publishing, 2008]. – ISBN 978-0-143-41574-9, Rs. 299.

ONE KNOWS TODAY next to nothing about Dr Anton Alois Führer (1853-1930), introduced by writer Charles Allen as a “fairly minor character” (p. vi). His role during the early imperial excavations of Buddhist sites northern of the Ganges was nonetheless justifiably greater than acknowledged by the short history of Indian archaeology during the Raj. The rewriting of his moves, publications, fantastic suppositions and absurd forgeries was by no means an easy task, due to the neglect of such tertiary characters sunk ever since into oblivion. British writer and historian Allen (born in colonial India) chooses to unearth Führer’s activity at the end of 19th century and its tricky legacy, well beyond his disappearance from public record, and to rewrite the faltering history of the modern identification of the Buddha’s birthplace, which included many more individuals over four generations and a decent bunch of related circumstances.

Everything of note rests here upon the neglected archive from Piprahwa of the Scot colonial landowner William Claxton Peppé (b. 1852), owner of Birdpore Estate. The story starts on 18 January 1898 at Piprahwa Kot, a mound excavated by Peppé with an extraordinary result: five vessels with no less than some 2,000 artefacts, all discovered unbroken, and almost by chance. They contained all kinds of materials such as gold and silver, pearls and beads of many a sort, cornelians and crystals, topazes, lapis lazuli, and amethysts (a first complete inventory on pp. 76-77). At that moment, one may recall, the Buddha’s birthplace of Kapilavastu was among the last most important Buddhist sites still to be located during that both magnificently global and shadowy in many a respect rediscovery of Buddhism started one century or so before. Willie Peppé had no specific acquaintance with things Buddhist, so he wrote on the spot two letters to the scholar archaeologists he knew: to Vincent Arthur Smith (then in Gorakhpur), better known than perhaps every other single colonial personality evoked in this book (except of course Georg Bühler), and to “Reverend and Doctor of Philosophy Anton Alois Führer” (p. 32), the then Lucknow Museum employee, a defrocked Catholic early in the 1880s, then already doing some excavation in Nepal. Significant as they might have been, the artefacts were easily superseded by a Brāhmī inscription since then famous, which simply located the treasure, its stūpa, and the entire micro-region as vital for the last days of the Buddha and its relics. The Piprahwa fund immediately allowed situating better the first and last

period of the Buddha's biography, thus promising to close the foundational period of Buddhist archaeology in northern India. The last vacant spots on the map of early Buddhist India were to be filled in.

Both Smith and Führer obligingly replied with informative comments, and a couple of days later visited themselves the Birdpore Estate. Such early triangle of persons reputedly interpreting of their own accord the remains and inscription would later cast a threefold shadow on the allegations of forgery the story retold by Allen will soon contain (that "sort of conspiracy involving the removal of objects from one excavation to another and the forging of an inscription", p. 107). Their campaigns were followed by L. A. Waddell's initiatives, some of them abortive (well known to Tibetologists, he is described "by all accounts, a disagreeable and peevish character with a very high opinion of himself", p. 133).

We then start to follow some ravages of rivalry, in a landscape that would soon become of most significant note for every Buddhist scholar¹. Smith ("perhaps a less than agreeable colleague", p. 80) met in 1898 a 'colleague' who published a pamphlet under his name that undergoes some 90% of plagiarism. Meanwhile, Andrew Huxley (cf. *infra*) has put forward other, no less relevant data of frighteningly unscrupulous and deliberately prejudiced procedures. Führer was strongly backed at the beginning by Georg Bühler in Vienna, without a doubt one of the best Sanskrit scholars in the West ever, and a scholar who generously funded Führer's excavation ventures in Nepal, but his Bombay pupil plagiarized him without much ado, and the pages Allen writes about the possibly suspicious death of Bühler are intriguing indeed (Bühler drowned, alone in his boat on Lake Constance, on April 8, 1898). Moreover, there are strong reasons to assume nowadays that Führer not only faked the major inscription for locating there the

¹ Gadjin Nagao for example wrote: "[w]e are able to pinpoint the location of Lumbini from the pillar erected there by King Aśoka (mid-third century B.C.) that was discovered at the end of the last century. In 1958 I travelled from this Lumbini to where there are remains of what is presumed to be Kapilavastu, a journey of about 19 miles. There were only extremely poor roads that traversed the fields, and the jeep shook like a boat coursing through stormy seas. The two and a half hour trip would have been far easier, it seemed, had we gone by elephant back." See G. M. NAGAO, "The Life of the Buddha: An Interpretation", *Eastern Buddhist* 20 (1987), no. 2, pp. 1-31 (transl. by Mark L. Blum of Chap. 2 from *Bukkyō no genryū: Indo*, Osaka: Osaka Shoshei Kabushiki Gaisha, 1984), here 8. This may remind of much older Buddhist attitudes. Before going forth, the monks that rode in the very forests of Kapilavastu in a chariot, as explained by the Buddha in the *Upadeśa*, "did not notice the distances. Now that you are in monks' robes (*cīvara*) with begging-bowl (*pātra*) in hand, your fatigue (*śrama*) is extreme and you take into account the length of the path", see Étienne LAMOTTE, *Le Traité de la grande vertu de sagesse de Nāgārjuna (Mahāprajñāpāramitāsāstra)*, Louvain: Bibliothèque du Muséon 18 (for vol. 1-2), Publ. de l'Institut orientaliste de Louvain 2, 12, 14 (for vol. 3-5), 1944 [repr. 1966], 1949 [repr. 1967], 1970, 1976, 1980, here vol. 5, p. 2296. For more on Kapilavastu in Indic and Chinese sources, see vol. 1, p. 459 n. 1, vol. 2, pp. 868 and 1005, vol. 3, p. 1586.

Buddha's birthplace, but also faked it in different stages, plagiarizing the emendations of the then armchair Indian epigraphy of Bühler on his very Nepal finds.

For the historian of early South Asian religions, it would be fruitful to meditate again about the fastidious fate of the linkage between translations of Buddhist texts and their close, though sometimes implausible, reading by major archaeologists aiming at mapping their minutiae's description. All the dramatis personae of this story carried copies of those few French or English extant translation of Faxian and Xuanzang. Chinese pilgrim reports at hand, they sometimes wrestled with the changes intruded since then, less with those until that time. They all relied, for a significant period, on the (mis)calculation by Cunningham of a *yojana* equivalent to 6.71 miles (see p. 87 and *passim*; but also one awkward calculation of 'less than 1 yojana [c. 82 miles]' on p. 102). Gone the era of Führer, Smith and the like, Allen opts for letting us know which the major developments were regarding the same recurrent queries up to nowadays. Remarkably less happened, it seems, before 1947. Nevertheless, a thick shadow had covered significant parts of Indian (and Nepalese) postcolonial archaeological advances. Historical contention between Nepal and India also reflects major and minor episodes of the plot, and once, as the Nepal Durbar gave no permission to archaeologists to cross its frontier, Smith received "a rap over the knuckles for his improper conduct" (p. 107).

To the instigation of Allen is to be endorsed the organization of an international workshop which, with the help of the Royal Asiatic Society and the Buddhist Society in London, purposely addressed the key problems still unsettled, and Allen's story undoubtedly benefited much from them. Leading scholars, no at least the best epigraphists worldwide – as Lance Cousins, Richard Gombrich, Oskar von Hinüber, and Richard Salomon – took eventually part in a 2006 gathering from which no scholarly publication seems available. The Piprahwa inscription appears to be unquestionably authentic, as Salomon admits: "[n]ormally, a clever forger will borrow terminology and style from genuine inscriptions, but the relatively few reliquary inscriptions that were known at the time of the discovery of Piprahwa inscription have no significant textual resemblance to it. [...] Forgeries tend to be either blatant imitations of genuine inscriptions, or totally aberrant texts [...] Despite its anomalous character in comparison to other relic inscription, the Piprahwa inscription rings true in all regards. Its language, for example, is a good example of Ardhmāgadhī, as manifested, for example, by the dialectally characteristic epenthesis in the last word, *sakiyānaṃ* = Sanskrit *śākyānām*" (quoted pp. 261-262). Nevertheless, from that workshop nothing appeared in print as far as we know. We do have instead a 2010 contribution by Andrew Huxley, which covers the first forty years of Führer's career (without discussing or mentioning the book under review)¹, with

¹ Andrew HUXLEY, "Dr Führer's Wanderjahre: the Early Career of a Victorian Archaeologist", *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* 20 (2010), no. 4, pp. 489-502 (here 489). Allen seems to take the later 'career' of Führer as less fraudulent; this is however far from truth, as Huxley reopens the file of his later Burmese forgeries.

portrayals which transfer additional interest for such patient inquiries into the enigmas of the field: “[b]etween 1894 and 1899 Führer displayed the hubris, and suffered the nemesis, of a Sophoclean protagonist”. As Allen writes, “[i]f Prof. Bühler ever saw a copy of that preliminary report [of the alleged Kāpilavastu findings] the sheer audacity of Führer’s claims to have found and read no less than eighteen pre-Asokan inscriptions must have set the alarm bells ring” (p. 166). Most baffling, also since “no element of financial fraud seems to have been involved” (pp. 168-169), Führer sent to U Ma in Burma fake relics of the Buddha, and did that with the ordinary and secure attitude good for every colonial commodity: he sent ‘relics’ – always more Nepalese ‘relics’ and even before entering Nepal! – by post.

Allen opts again to be boldly anti-Saidian, without however weighting heavy arguments in this respect, and being rather unconvincing. For him, Said’s 1978 opus is “a regrettably unscholarly book” (p. vii). Nonetheless, the massive scrutiny of that book during most of the several decades, of which Allen seems only to know a too tiny portion, noticed nothing similar to Allen’s considerations (p. xii) of Indian very contemporary politics, where “it is not impossible that the next decade may see Mayawati and the BSP governing India”, which are simply out of place (not in the Saidian sense). From the other, Nepalese angle, it should be noted that this book written “over a winter in Nepal” owes in his criticism of archaeological conduct in the formerly royal Nepal something to the recent political uprising, which furthermore cannot possibly stand scholarly scrutiny. To recount a “life of the Buddha”, as the author did in the first chapter, needs a better training or a more careful editorship. No starting manual of Buddhism speaks, for instance, of the Buddha’s “fifty-one years of teaching”. Unfamiliarity with major ancient works in Indian languages or at least reliable translations led him to consider one description by Führer as genuinely modern (p. 163: as “most extravagant purple prose”): to keep it simple, one probable source of Führer’s rather strict paraphrase (here the *Nidānakathā* I, p. 62), is fairly adequate.

There are dozens of helpful photos¹, plans and maps as well as twelve colour plates (all unnumbered) inserted in the main text. Some of them, even if this is not clearly indicated, were previously unpublished, and adduce much further evidence from the context of discovery. It is nevertheless a pity that the transliterations of terms in Indic languages is so poorly supervised (no, selective or cruelly misspelled diacritics), and that instead of *mahāparinirvāṇa* we find everywhere “Maharaparinirvana”². Sylvain Lévi is always “Silvain” (pp. 43, 239), alas, one “French linguist” (p. 151). There are too many other unfortunate proofs of ignorance: T. W. Rhys Davids cannot possibly be considered “to all intents a Buddhist himself” (p. 237), and the misspellings of non-English words are legion (e.g. *Bauhinia purpurria* [p. 2] instead of *purpurea*), unworthy for the book’s

¹ Führer’s contested legacy was a scandal indeed: as the author notes concerning a photo of Kankali Tila excavation in 1886-1887, even “[t]he original photograph was removed from the photographic records of his Archeological Survey Department after his forced resignation” (p. 71).

² I conform: see pp. vii, 6 (thrice), 9, 13 (twice), 14, 19, 63, 65, 66, 93, 121, 160, 201, 225; an ‘exception’ (“*Mahaparinirvana sutanta*”) on p. 263.

importation and publishers. Some rather lengthy discussions (p. 11 sq. and *passim*) of the massacre of the Śākya would greatly benefit from an article of BAREAU¹. One can nevertheless, even with such mixed feelings, follow and enjoy this story belonging to the early days of Buddhist Studies and sometimes phantasmal indeed colonial archaeology. Story of some hugely mind-boggling frauds, which has as always the virtue to enlighten us eloquently about the aims of that science some tried in vain to cheat², persistently as we are in need of fairness.

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¹ André BAREAU, “Le massacre des Śākya: essai d’interprétation”, *BEFEO* 69 (1981), pp. 45-73, repr. in his posthumous *Recherches sur la biographie du Buddha dans les Sūtrapiṭaka et les Vinayapiṭaka anciens*, vol. III : *Articles complémentaires*, Publ. de l’EFEO 178, Paris: EFEO, 1995, pp. 277-305 (not having historical consistency, but being an episode entirely invented in 2nd century BCE, and then amalgamated by other traditions, up to Kṣemendra).

² Indic forgeries as sometimes supreme task for philologists – to remember a most unfortunate episode in Hoernle’s career (here p. 170) – are magnificently described recently by Richard SALOMON, “The Fine Art of Forgery in India”, in Gérard COLAS, Gerdi GERSCHHEIMER (eds.), *Écrire et transmettre en Inde classique / Writing and transmitting in Premodern India*, Paris: École française d’Extrême-Orient, 2009, pp. 107-134; see also the review article by Sheldon POLLOCK, “Indian Philology and India’s Philology”, *JA* 299 (2011), no. 1, pp. 423-442 (here 429-431).

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